

Naturally Occurring 1,7-Diarylheptanoids

PER CLAESON^{a,b}, PATOOMRATANA TUCHINDA^a and VICHAI REUTRAKUL^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Mahidol University, Rama VI Road, Bangkok 10400, Thailand

^bDepartment of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Rangsit University, Pahonyotin Road, Patumtani 12000, Thailand

Manuscript received 1 February 1994

The diarylheptanoids comprise a distinct class of naturally occurring compounds, which display the unique structural feature aryl-C₇-aryl. Within this class are the linear diarylheptanoids, which differ individually in the functional groups on the aryl- and C₇-moieties. Diarylheptanoids further appear as cyclophanes : macrocyclic biarylheptanoids and macrocyclic diaryl ether heptanoids. A few unusual diarylheptanoids with cyclised C₇-chains have also been reported. Several diarylheptanoid glycosides (mono-, di-, or tri-glycosides of glucose, xylose or apiose), and some tannin and phenylbutanoid derivatives of diarylheptanoids have been isolated.

There have been few reports on the biological activities of diarylheptanoids, most of which appearing in the areas of antiinflammatory and antihepatotoxic effects. The pharmacologically most extensively studied compound is curcumin (71), which has been reported to exhibit several biological activities, e.g. antiinflammatory, antispasmodic and antihepatotoxic effects¹. Several diarylheptanoids have been shown to inhibit prostaglandin and/or leukotriene biosynthesis *in vitro*²⁻⁶. The structure-activity relationship of antihepatotoxic diarylheptanoids has been investigated. It was concluded that free hydroxyl groups in the aryl moieties was a major structural requirement for potent antihepatotoxic effect⁷.

The diarylheptanoids have a limited distribution in nature. Hitherto, they have been found exclusively in seven plant families : Aceraceae (the Maple family), Betulaceae (the Birch family),

Burseraceae (the Incense family), Casuarinaceae (the Beefwood family), Fabaceae (Leguminosae; the Pea family), Myricaceae (the Waxmyrtle family) and Zingiberaceae (the Ginger family), with the largest numbers occurring in Zingiberaceae and Betulaceae (cf. Table 6).

Curcumin (71) the major orange pigment of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), is the most well-known diarylheptanoid and it has given rise to the designation curcuminoids, which is commonly applied to diarylheptanoids of the phenolic linear type. Curcumin was isolated in 1815 by Vogel and Pelletier. The structure elucidation and the first synthesis were reported in 1910 and 1913, respectively^{8,9}. Up to 1964, only three new diarylheptanoids (68, 69¹⁰ and 115¹¹) were isolated. Subsequently, a total of approximately 120 naturally occurring diarylheptanoids of various types have been described. This review covers reports on naturally occurring 1,7-diarylheptanoids appearing in major journals from 1953 to October 1993. Leading references on the total synthesis of diarylheptanoids are given in the respective sections. Based on their chemical structures, the diarylheptanoids have been grouped into five major types : (I) non-phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (Table 1), (II) phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (Table 2), (III) macrocyclic biarylheptanoids (Table 3), (IV) macrocyclic diaryl ether heptanoids (Table 4) and (V) diarylheptanoids with cyclised C₇-chain (Table 5). Tables 1-5 list the diarylheptanoids with trivial names, occurrence in nature and pertinent literature references.

Non-phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (Type I)

The Type I diarylheptanoids have been isolated only from plants in the families Betulaceae and Zingiberaceae. The known non-phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (1–15, Table 1) all have unsubstituted aryl groups and could thus be designated diphenylheptanoids. The first compound of this type, yashabushiketol (12) was reported in 1969 by Asakawa and coworkers¹². The Type I diarylheptanoids all have an oxygen function in 3-position in the C₇-chain. Variations of functional groups on the hydrocarbon chain are the additional oxygenation at C₁ and/or C₅ (1–8, 10–12, 15), the 1,2-double bond (9–12) and the conjugated diene moiety (13–15). No non-phenolic linear diarylheptanoid glycosides have been reported.

TABLE 1—NON-PHENOLIC LINEAR DIARYLHEPTANOIDS

Compd no	Trivial name	Occurrence ^a	Ref
1	Yashabushidiol B	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> (Be)	45
2	—	<i>Alnus fruticosa</i> (Be) <i>Alnus mandshurica</i> (Be)	46 cf 45 46 cf 45
3	Yashabushidiol A	<i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z) <i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> (Be)	47 45
4	Dihydroyashabushiketol	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> ^b (Be) <i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	12, 48–52 2, 5, 53, 54
5	—	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	54
6	Yashabushitriol	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> (Be)	45
7	Yashabushiketodiol A	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> (Be)	45
8	Yashabushiketodiol B	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> (Be)	45
9	—	<i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z) <i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	47 3
10	—	<i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z)	47
11	—	<i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z)	47
12	Yashabushiketol	<i>Alnus sieboldiana</i> ^b (Be)	12, 49, 50
13	—	<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	3
14	Alnustone	<i>Alnus pendula</i> (Be) <i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z) <i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	52, 55, 56 47 3
15	—	<i>Alpinia katsumadae</i> (Z)	47

^a(Be)=Betulaceae, (Z)=Zingiberaceae ^b*Alnus firma* was originally given as the source of this compound^{12,48,49}, but the botanical identity was later revised to *A sieboldiana*⁵⁷

	R ₁	R ₂
1	— OH	— OH
2	— OH	— OH
3	— OH	— OH
4	= O	— OH
5	= O	— OMe

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
6	— OH	— OH	— OH
7	— OH	= O	— OH
8	— OH	= O	— OH

	R ₁	R ₂
9	— H	— OH
10	— OH	— OH
11	— OH	= O
12	= O	— OH

	R ₁	R ₂
13	— H	— OH
14	— H	= O
15	— OH	= O

TABLE 2—PHENOLIC LINEAR DIARYLHEPTANOIDS

Table-2 (contd.)

Compd. no.	Trivial name	Occurrence ^d	Ref.				
				43	Hirsutanonol	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	66, 76
						<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	52
						<i>Alnus serrulatooides</i> (Be)	52, 75
16	(-)-Centrololobol	<i>Centrolobium tomentosum</i> (F)	41, 42, 58	44	-	<i>Alnus serrulatooides</i> (Be)	52, 75
		<i>Centrolobium sclerophyllum</i> (F)	42	45	Oregonin	<i>Alnus rubra</i> (Be)	77
		<i>Centrolobium paraense</i>				<i>Alnus serrulatooides</i> (Be)	52, 75, 79
		var. <i>paraense</i> (F)	42			<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	52
		<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59			<i>Alnus hirsuta</i>	
17	(+)-Centrololobol ^b	<i>Centrolobium robustum</i> (F)	41, 42			var. <i>microphylla</i> (Be)	19
		<i>Centrolobium sp.</i> (F)	58		Hirsutoside	(Be)	78
		<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	43	46	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	80
18	Aceroside VII	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	61	47	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	80
		<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59	48	Hexahydrocurcumin	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	Alpinin ¹¹ ; 81
19	Aceroside VIII	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	61			<i>ficinarum</i> (Z)	54
		<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59			<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	65
20	-	<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59	49	Hirsunin	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i>	
21	Aceroside X	<i>Acer griseum</i> (A)	62			var. <i>microphylla</i> (Be)	19
22	Aceroside IX	<i>Acer griseum</i> (A)	62	50	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69
		<i>Acer triflorum</i> (A)	62	51	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69
23	Yakuchinone-A	<i>Alpinia oxyphylla</i> (Z)	22, 63, 64	52	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	54
24	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	65	53	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	2, 5
25	(-)-Hannokinol	<i>Centrolobium sclerophyllum</i> (F)	42	54	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	2
	(+)-Hannokinol	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	66	55	Yakuchinone-B	<i>Alpinia oxyphylla</i> (Z)	64, 82
		<i>Alnus japonica</i> ^c (Be)	67, 68	56	Dihydrocurcumin	<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Z)	83
26	-	<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	65			<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	65
		<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69, 70	57	-	<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	65
27	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69	58	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	54
28	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69	59	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	5
29	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69	60	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	2, 5, 53
30	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	71	61	-	<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	67, 68
31	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	70	62	Gingerenone C	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	23
32	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	71	63	Hirsutenone	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	66, 76
33	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	2,5	64	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69, 80
34	-	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i> (Z)	2, 5, 53, 54, 72	65	Gingerenone A	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	23, 71, 80
35	(+)-Hannokinin	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	66	66	Gingerenone B	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	23
		<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	52, 67, 68	67	Isogingerenone B	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	23
	Platyphyllone	<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59	68	Bisdemethoxycurcumin	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	84
36	Platyphyllloside (Platyphyllin)	<i>Betula platyphylla</i>				<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Z)	10, 85
		var. <i>japonica</i> (Be)	60, 73, 74			<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	86
		<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	25, 59			<i>Curcuma zeodaria</i> (Z)	87
37	-	<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59			<i>Zingiber zerumbet</i> (Z)	24
38	-	<i>Betula pendula</i> (Be)	59	69	Demethoxycurcumin	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	84
39	-	<i>Alnus serrulatooides</i> (Be)	52, 75			<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Z)	10, 85
40	-	<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	52			<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	86
41	-	<i>Alnus serrulatooides</i> (Be)	52, 75			<i>Curcuma zeodaria</i> (Z)	87
42	-	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> (Z)	69			<i>Zingiber zerumbet</i> (Z)	24

Table-2 (contd)

70	-	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	88
71	Curcumin ^d	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	84
		<i>Curcuma longa</i> (Z)	1, 10
		<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> (Z)	86
		<i>Curcuma zeodaria</i> (Z)	87
		<i>Zingiber zerumbet</i> (Z)	24
72	5'-Methoxycurcumin	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	84
73	Cassumunin A	<i>Zingiber cassumunar</i> (Z)	20
74	Cassumunin B	<i>Zingiber cassumunar</i> (Z)	20
75	Cassumunin C	<i>Zingiber cassumunar</i> (Z)	20
76	-	<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Z)	88

^a(A) = Aceraceae; (Be) = Betulaceae; (F) = Fabaceae; (Z) = Zingiberaceae. ^bConcerning the stereochemistry of 16 and 17 see Refs. 60, 61 ^cThe optical rotation of 25, isolated from *A. japonica*, was not reported^{67,68}. ^dFor additional references, see Ref. 1.

Dihydroyashabushiketol (4) has been shown *in vitro* to inhibit biosynthesis of the inflammatory mediators prostaglandins and leukotrienes^{2,5}. Compounds 9, 13 and 14 exerted significant anti-inflammatory activity in the assay of carragenin-induced hind paw edema in rats¹³.

Syntheses of various Type I diarylheptanoids have been reported¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

Phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (Type II)

Phenolic linear diarylheptanoids (16-76; Table 2) have been isolated mainly from plants in the families Betulaceae and Zingiberaceae, but a few have been reported from the Aceraceae and the Fabaceae (cf. Table 6).

This class of diarylheptanoids contains the largest number of compounds. Like the diphenylheptanoids, all Type II diarylheptanoids possess an oxygen function in 3-position of the C₇-chain. Further oxygenation of the C₇-chain occurs at positions 1 and/or 5. At least one aryl group is *p*-hydroxylated and additional substituents on the benzene rings are *meta*-hydroxy and/or *meta*-methoxy groups. Several Type II diarylheptanoids appear in nature as *O*-glycosides. Usually, the sugar part of the glycosides is attached to the oxygen in 3-position of the heptane chain (18-20,

	R ₁
16	- OH
17	- OH
18	- O-β-D-Glcp
19	- O-β D-Apuf-(1→6)-β-D-Glcp
20	- O-β D-Apuf-(1→2) [β D-Apuf-(1→6)]-β D-Glcp

	R ₁	R ₂
21	- H	- O-β D Glcp
22	- H	- O-β D-Apuf-(1→6) β-D-Glcp
23	- OMe	- H

24

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
25	- OH	- OH	- H	- H
26	- OH	- OH	- OMe	- OMe
27	- OH	- OH	- OMe	- OMe
28	- OAc	- OAc	- OH	- OH
29	- OAc	- OAc	- OMe	- OH
30	- OAc	- OAc	- OMe	- OMe

	R ₁	R ₂
31	- OH	- OH
32	- OAc	- OAc

	R ₁
33	— H
34	— OMe

	R ₁
35	— OH
36	— O-β-D-Glcp
37	— O-β-D-Apif-(1→6)-β-D-Glcp
38	— O-β-D-Apif-(1→2)-β-D-Glcp

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
39	— O-β-D-Xyl	— H	— OH
40	— OH	— OH	— H
41	— O-β-D-Xyl	— OH	— H
42	— OH	— OMe	— H
43	— OH	— OH	— OH
44	— O-β-D-Glc	— OH	— OH
45	— O-β-D-Xyl	— OH	— OH
46	— OH	— OH	— OMe
47	— OH	— OMe	— OH
48	— OH	— OMe	— OMe

36–39, 41 and 44–46), however, attachment through the *para*-hydroxy group (21 and 22) has also been found. No glycoside with an unsaturated C₇-chain has been reported. The novel compound hirsunin (49) is not only a glycoside but also a conjugate of the ellagitannin praecoxin A¹⁹. The cassumunins A-C (73–75) of *Zingiber cassumunar* are phenylbutanoid derivatives of curcumin (71), possessing antioxidant and antiin-

TABLE 3—MACROCYCLIC BIARYLHEPTANOIDS

Compd. no.	Trivial name	Occurrence ^a	Ref.
77	Myricanol	<i>Myrica nagi</i> (M) <i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	35, 89, 90 91, 92
78	Myricanol glucoside	<i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	91
79	Myricanol gentiobioside	<i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	93
80	—	<i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	93
81	5-Deoxymyricanone	<i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	92
82	Myricanone	<i>Myrica nagi</i> (M) <i>Myrica rubra</i> (M) <i>Myrica gale</i> (M)	35, 89 91, 92 94
83	13-Oxomyricanol	<i>Myrica nagi</i> (M)	95
84	Porson	<i>Myrica gale</i> (M) <i>Myrica rubra</i> (M)	96 92
85	Alnusdiol	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be) <i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be) <i>Casuarina junghuhniana</i> (C)	43 67, 68 98
86	Alnusonol	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be) <i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be) <i>Carpinus cordata</i> (Be)	43 52, 68, 97 29
87	Alnusoxide	<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be)	68, 97
88	—	<i>Carpinus cordata</i> (Be)	98
89	—	<i>Carpinus cordata</i> (Be)	99
90	Casuarinondiol	<i>Casuarina junghuhniana</i> (C)	29
91	—	<i>Carpinus cordata</i> (Be)	99
92	Monodeoxyasadanin	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be)	100
93	Asadanin	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be)	31, 32, 33 100, 101
94	Isoasadanol	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be)	100, 102
95	Epiasadanol	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be)	100, 101
96	Trideoxyasadanin-8-ene	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be) <i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	100 66
97	Dideoxyasadanin-8-ene	<i>Ostrya japonica</i> (Be)	100
98	Alnusone	<i>Alnus japonica</i> (Be) <i>Carpinus cordata</i> (Be)	68, 97 98
99	Garuganin V	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu)	30
100	Garuganin II	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu)	30, 38, 103

^a(Be) = Betulaceae; (Bu) = Burseraceae; (C) = Casuarinaceae; (M) = Myricaceae.

54

55

flammatory properties²⁰. The corresponding free phenylbutanoids have previously been reported from the same plant source²¹.

The pharmacological activities of curcumin (71) and extracts of *Curcuma longa* have been extensively studied. A review on this subject recently appeared¹. Antiinflammatory, antiulcerogenic, antispasmodic, antihepatotoxic, anticoagulant, anti-

TABLE 4—MACROCYCLIC DIARYL ETHER HEPTANOIDS

Compd. no.	Trivial name	Occurrence ^a	Ref
101	Acerogenin A	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	36, 104
102	Aceroside I	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	44, 105
103	Aceroside VI	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	106
104	Aceroside III	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	106
105	Aceroside IV	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	104
106	Acerogenin B	<i>Acer nikoense</i> (A)	104, 107
107	Galeon	<i>Myrica gale</i> (M)	37
108	Hydroxygaleon	<i>Myrica gale</i> (M)	37
109	Garugamblin-I	<i>Garuga gamblei</i> (Bu)	38, 108, 109
110	Garuganin IV	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu)	30
111	Garuganin III	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu)	110
112	Garuganin I	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu) <i>Garuga gamblei</i> (Bu)	111, 112 108
113	Garugamblin-2	<i>Garuga gamblei</i> (Bu)	38, 108, 109
114	Garuganin VI	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> (Bu)	30

^a(A) = Aceraceae; (Bu) = Burseraceae; (M) = Myricaceae

fertility, antitumor, antibacterial and antifungal activities, as well as effects on wound healing, bile production, lipid metabolism, pancreas function and on the cardiovascular system were described.

A number of Type II diarylheptanoids have been reported to inhibit prostaglandin and leukotriene biosynthesis *in vitro*²⁻⁵ and to have antihepatotoxic effects⁷. Yakuchinone A (23) has been shown to exhibit cardiotoxic effect²². Gingerenone A (65), an important constituent of *Zingiber officinale*, possesses antifungal and anticoccidium properties²³. Compounds 68, 69 and 71 (curcumin) have been reported to exhibit cytotoxic activity *in vitro*²⁴. Platyphylloside (36) has been found to inhibit ruminant digestibility *in vitro* and was proposed to be involved in a chemical plant defense system against browsers²⁵.

A general biosynthetic pathway leading to 1,7-diarylheptanoids, with special reference to curcumin (71), has been put forward^{9,26}. The molecule was proposed to derive from two cinnamate (C₆-C₃) units linked to a central methylene group

	R ₁	R ₂
58	— H	— H
59	— OH	— OMe
60	— H	— OMe

	R ₁	R ₂
61	— H	— H
62	— OMe	— H
63	— OH	— OH
64	— OMe	— OH
65	— OMe	— OMe

	R ₁	R ₂
66	— H	— OMe
67	— OMe	— H

	R ₁	R ₂
68	— H	— H
69	— OMe	— H
70	— OMe	— OH
71	— OMe	— OMe

provided by malonate. The hypothesis was partly substantiated by *in vivo* feeding of radioactively labelled precursors to *Curcuma longa* plants, but the experimental results were not entirely con-

 TABLE 5—DIARYLHEPTANOIDS, WITH CYCLISED C₇-CHAIN

Compd. no.	Trivial name	Occurrence ^a	Ref.
115	(+)-De-O-methyl-centrolobin	<i>Centrolobium robustum</i> (F)	41, 42
		<i>Centrolobium sp.</i> (F)	58
116	(-)-De-O-methyl-centrolobin	<i>Centrolobium tomentosum</i> (F)	41, 42, 58
		<i>Centrolobium paraense</i> var. <i>paraense</i> (F)	
		<i>Centrolobium sclerophyllum</i> (F)	42
117	(+)-Centrolobin	<i>Centrolobium robustum</i> (F)	11, 40, 41, 42, 58
		<i>Centrolobium sp.</i> (F)	
	(-)-Centrolobin	<i>Centrolobium tomentosum</i> (F)	41, 42, 58
117	—	<i>Alnus hirsuta</i> (Be)	43

^a(Be) = Betulaceae; (F) = Fabaceae.

clusive. An alternative biosynthetic pathway involving polyketide extension of a cinnamate group with five acetate (malonate) units, followed by cyclisation to form the second phenyl ring was considered^{9,26}.

The total syntheses of several Type II diarylheptanoids have been reported^{8,16,27,28}.

TABLE 6—TAXONOMIC DISTRIBUTION OF DIARYLHEPTANOIDS

Plant family	Genus with diarylheptanoids	Type ^a and (in parenthesis) number of diarylheptanoids
Aceraceae	<i>Acer</i>	II (4); IV (6)
Betulaceae	<i>Alnus</i>	I (9); II (12); III (5); V (1)
	<i>Betula</i>	II (8)
	<i>Carpinus</i>	III (5)
	<i>Ostrya</i>	III (6)
Burseraceae	<i>Garuga</i>	III (2); IV (6)
Casuarinaceae	<i>Casuarina</i>	III (2)
Fabaceae	<i>Centrolobium</i>	II (3); V (4)
Myricaceae	<i>Myrica</i>	III (8); IV (2)
Zingiberaceae	<i>Alpinia</i>	I (8); II (12)
	<i>Curcuma</i>	I (3); II (10)
	<i>Zingiber</i>	II (24)

^aType I : Non-phenolic linear diarylheptanoids; Type II : Phenolic linear diarylheptanoids; Type III : Macrocyclic biarylheptanoids; Type IV : Macrocyclic diaryl ether heptanoids; Type V : Diarylheptanoids with cyclised C₇-chain.

87

88

Macrocyclic biarylheptanoids (Type III)

A majority of the macrocyclic biarylheptanoids (77-100; Table 3) has been reported from the two plant families Betulaceae and Myricaceae, but four compounds of this class (85 and 90; 99 and 100) have recently been isolated from the Casuarinaceae²⁹ and the Burseraceae³⁰, respectively.

The first *meta-meta*-bridged macrocyclic biarylheptanoid, asadanin (93) was described in 1965 by Yasue³¹⁻³³. Subsequently, approximately 25 different diarylheptanoids of this type (Table 3) have been reported. Two glycosides (78 and 79) and one galloyl glycoside (80) of the pivotal myricanol (77) have been isolated. The total syntheses of myricanol and myricanone (82) have been accomplished³⁴.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
89	— H	— OH	— H
90	— OH	— H	— OH

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
98	— H	— OH	— H
99	— OMe	— OMe	— H
100	— OMe	— OMe	— OMe

91

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
92	— OH	— OH	= O	— H
93	— OH	— OH	= O	— OH
94	— OH	— OH	— OH	— OH
95	— OH	— OH	— OH	— OH

	R ₁
96	— H
97	— OH

The conformation of the macrocyclic biarylheptanoids have been investigated by X-ray analysis of a brominated derivative of myricanol. It was found that the molecule is twisted in such a way that the biaryl unit is not co-planar and its axis distorted from linearity due to the carbon chain tether³⁵.

Apart from a brief statement that myricanol (77) exhibits moderate insect-repelling activity³⁴, no reports on biological activities of the Type III diarylheptanoids have appeared.

Macrocyclic diaryl ether heptanoids (Type IV)

Type IV diarylheptanoids (101–104; Table 4) have been isolated from plants of the families Aceraceae, Burseraceae and Myricaceae (Table 4).

The *meta-para* cyclophanes acerogenin A (101) from *Acer nikoense*³⁶, galeon (107) and hydroxy-galeon (108) from *Myrica gale*³⁷ were described in 1976, as the first macrocyclic ether linked diarylheptanoids. Galeon has been shown by X-ray diffraction analysis to have a conformation in which the two aryl rings are approximately perpendicular to each other³⁷. An interesting feature of this spatial arrangement is that the aromatic proton *ortho* to the ether linkage of the *meta*-bridged aryl group is located within the shielding cone of the neighbouring aromatic ring; consequently, the signal of this proton appears at

	R ₁	R ₂
101	—OH	—OH
102	—OH	—O-β-D-Glcp
103	—O-β-D-Glcp	—OH
104	—O-β-D-Apif-(1→6)-β-D-Glcp	—OH
105	=O	—O-β-D-Glcp

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
106	—H	—OH	—H
107	—H	=O	—OMe
108	—OH	=O	—OMe

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
109	—H	—H	—OMe
110	—H	—OMe	—H
111	—H	—OMe	—OMe
112	—OMe	—H	—OMe
113	—H	—O-CH ₂ -O—	

114

an unusually high field (ca δ 4.9–5.8) in the ^1H nmr spectrum^{30,36,37}.

Glycosides with the sugar moiety attached either to the *meta*-bridged aryl ring (102 and 105), or to the C₇-chain (103 and 104) have been reported. Garuganin VI (114) displays the unique structural feature of two geminal methyl groups on carbon number 4 of the C₇-chain³⁰. As a notable fact, the diarylheptanoids reported from the Burseraceae (109–114) all lack phenolic character (Table 4).

Garuganin I (112) was briefly stated to have antibiotic effect³⁸, but no other biological activities of Type IV diarylheptanoids have been reported.

The total synthesis of garugamblin I (109) was recently reported³⁹.

Diarylheptanoids with cyclised C₇-chain (Type V)

The Type V diarylheptanoids constitute the

smallest group of the diarylheptanoids and at present only five compounds are known (Table 5). (+)-Centrolobin (116) was first reported in 1964, by Marini-Bettolo and co-workers, as a bacteriostatic substance from *Centrolobium robustum*¹¹. A synthesis of racemic centrolobin was reported in the following year by the same group⁴⁰. The optical antipodes of centrolobin and its de-*O*-methyl derivative (115) have been claimed to be useful as chemotaxonomic markers of different *Centrolobium* spp.^{41,42}. The interesting and unusual diarylheptanoid 117 was isolated from *Alnus hirsuta*⁴³.

	R ₁
115	— OH
116	— OMe

117

Concluding remarks : The taxonomic distribution of diarylheptanoids has been summarised in Table 6. The taxonomically very widely separated plant families Betulaceae (Dicotyledon) and Zingiberaceae (Monocotyledon) contain the highest numbers of diarylheptanoids. None of the genera in Zingiberaceae have been reported to have diarylheptanoids of the macrocyclic types (types III and IV), whereas *Alnus* of Betulaceae and *Acer* of Aceraceae contain both linear (Types I and II) and macrocyclic diarylheptanoids. It has been proposed that the macrocyclic diarylheptanoids are biosynthesised by intramolecular oxidative couplings of linear 1,7-diarylheptanoids⁸ and the co-occurrence of e.g. aceroside VII (**18**) and aceroside VI (**103**) (Types II and IV) in *Acer nikoense*, and hannokinol (**25**) and alnusdiol (**85**) (Types II and III) in *Alnus japonica*, supports this proposal. It is interesting to note that both macrocyclic biaryl- and diaryl ether heptanoids have been reported to occur in *Myrica gale* (**84** and **107**) and *Garuga pinnata* (**99** and **107**). No linear diarylheptanoids have, however, been found in these plants (c.f. Tables 3, 4 and 6).

Surprisingly, few studies have reported pharmacological activities of diarylheptanoids, despite the fact that many of the plants that yield them are reputed to have medicinal properties, e.g. *Myrica nagi*³⁴, *Garuga pinnata*³⁰ and *Acer nikoense*⁴⁴. An exception to this is curcumin (**71**), from *Curcuma longa* and other plant species, on which an extensive body of investigations exists¹. Further investigations of the biological activities of this chemically unique class of secondary plant metabolites would very likely yield highly interesting results.

Acknowledgement

The financial support from the International Program in the Chemical Sciences (Uppsala, Sweden) is gratefully acknowledged.

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